

ANALYSIS OF THE REFLECTION ON THE DEFECTS OF THE SOCIETY IN "OLIVER TWIST" BY CHARLES DICKENS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the reflection of social problems of that time in the work of "Oliver Twist" by Charles Dickens. In "Oliver Twist" children are presented as powerless. There is nothing they can do in society so they have no chance but to steal. Whilst at the same time the rich people can do whatever they want and live well.

Key words: Orphan, homeless, rich, steal, poor, lonely, criminal, violence, thieves, corrupt

I. Introduction

One of the main themes of all Charles Dickens' novels was how the poorest people in society were treated the worst. This is one of the key themes in Oliver Twist, where we can see the failure of the workhouse system that was unable to look after the poor and lonely orphans that were in their care.

"Oliver Twist" is a novel, it is realistic fiction at the time it was published. 'Oliver Twist' was Dickens' second novel, it was published in 1837-8 and was important of childhood deprivation during the Victorian era. Dickens was one of the first 'celebrities' to become very famous for his writing.

In the story Oliver's mother Agnes has died in the workhouse celebrities's birth with revealing who his father was. Oliver is brought up as an orphan and moved at the age of 9 to the workhouse. When it comes to say about the characters, some critics observed that Oliver Twist is merely a passive pawn in the deadly match between good and evil. It is further stipulated that the "good" characters, such as Mr. Brownlow and the Maylies, pale in comparison to the villains Fagan and Bill Sikes.

In this research, I would like to analyze the education values that can be found in the Charles Dickens 'novel entitled "Oliver Twist". To give evidence of this study, the writer presents studies that have been conducted in the different study.

Ariyanti investigated An Analysis of Education values of the novel "Bumi Manusia". The method that is used in this study is descriptive qualitative method, which focused on textual data analysis.

Pramoedya Ananta Toer on his novel talks about three main characters: Minke, Annelies and Nyai Onto Soroh. He tells about motivation to get better education that have to get out from Javanese culture, family life and struggle of love. The result is many educational values can be learned by reader.

Moreover, many educational values can be implicated in Indonesian education. The novel gives information, motivation to the reader.

Muntamah with her study entitled An Analysis of moral Values As Seen on Charles Dickens Novel Oliver Twist: In this research, Muntamah used Descriptive Qualitative Research. She utilized the documentation method in collecting the data while in data analysis. She used observation and taking notes technique and also looked for other information which related to

the research problems. The results of this research shows that there are some moral values that can be found in “ Oliver Twist “ those are braver, humbleness, honesty , steadfastness, sympathetic to others, cooperativeness, thankfulness, kind-hearted, trustworthiness, sincerity, love and affection.

Nasrudinillah stated in his paper entitled The Analysis Of Educational Values on “ Front Of The Class” Movie. In his paper he used qualitative study; he took the primary data from audiovisual and scrip from “Front of the Class” movie.

The secondary data is taken from many literary books and some relevant materials to support and complete the primary data sources. The result of this study is that are some educational values in the “Front of the Class” movie like: never give up, self-confidence, friendly and be polite, love, forgiveness, optimism, help each other and responsible as human society.

Saputra (2012) also conducted a library research entitled An Analysis of Educational Values in “ Ranah 3 Warna” Novel. The result of this research he found some educational values such as life is a struggle, education is human right, never give up, be patient but not passive, the power of dream, respect to parent, respect to teacher, be optimistic in life, be confident.

Kustantiningrum (2012) in her thesis entitled An Analysis of Educational Values in Andrea Hirata's Novel “The Rainbow Troops” stated that she found some educational values, it can be mentioned as follow: Struggle, skill-discover, responsible, hard work and life attitude, discipline, religious, independent, social concern, communicative, and honest. The educational values were shown by the six main characters, they are: 1) Lintang, 2) Mahar, 3) Ikal, 4) Bu Mus, 5) Pak Harfan, 6) Lintang's father.

Hasanah in her thesis entitled An Analysis of Materiali Lintan the Reflection of Reflectio In 1837 in Charles Dickens’ Oliver Twist. The result finds that Oliver Twist

Is the reflection of Industrial Revolution. Its society deals with the poverty and affects the people to be a materialist. People will do anything to recover from their economic condition. They try to get the money as much as they can. Dickens as the author wants to criticize about the condition of England related to the children labor and poverty.

Estiyana in her publication article entitled Child Exploitation Reflected in Charles Dickens’ Oliver Twist Novel: A Sociological Approach. She stated that based on sociological analysis, the writer is find five aspects such as social aspect, economic aspect, cultural aspect, religious aspect, and science and technology aspect based on Oliver Twist novel by Charles Dickens. The cause and affects of Oliver Twist by Charles Dickens”.

Based on the previous studies elaborated above, my thesis proposal focuses on An Analysis of Moral Education to Charles Dickens “Oliver Twist “. The uniqueness of this proposal is that the researchers analyzed the education from the perspective of moral based on the Oliver Twist.

Dickens lived a tragic life in his lifetime, which caused him has a strong sense of kindness to the poor at the bottom of the society. Oliver in the novel as a representative of the poor and the social lower class, also lived a miserable life . On the basis of the three subsystems in attitude system, the paper mainly analyzes the discourse that relates to Oliver at the lexical level.

The rise and fall in society through the corrupting power of money is also an important theme of the novel. The novel which is of a simple structure, deals with the development of the protagonist Oliver. Dickens describes the phases of Oliver's progress in terms of a child's instinctive and therefore virtuous response to his natural surrounding and in terms of negation

of childhood simplicity. Oliver is a member of that vast and cruel machine of the Victorian society with its obsession with money and class distinction. Oliver is presented as a Dickensian orphan who is harshly treated and brought up by hand.

Oliver's inability to speak at his trial due to exhaustion and illness serves as a metaphor for the lower class's lack of political power and ability to address its own issues in public. The ability to vote in 1830s England was based on money, so the poor had no say in legislation. Furthermore, the upper classes project their own ideas about the poor into them, to the point where impoverished people's identities are casually rewritten with little regard for reality. Oliver is unable to speak his own name due to exhaustion and anxiety, so a court official assigns him the fictitious identity "Tom White". Throughout the hearing, Oliver is incorrectly referred to as a "young vagrant" and a "hardened scoundrel" before being declared "guilty. Mr. Bumble creates the name Oliver Twist" after Oliver is born, making it no longer legal. As these examples demonstrate, Oliver's identity has been shaped throughout his life by more powerful individuals.

For a long time after it was ushered into this world of sorrow and trouble by the parish surgeon, it remained a matter of considerable doubt whether the child would survive to bear any name at all in which case it is somewhat more than probable that these memoirs would never have appeared; or, if they had that being comprised within a couple of pages, they would have possessed the inestimable merit of being the most concise and faithful specimen of biography, extant in the literature of any age or country.

IV. Discussion

Example- 1

For the next eight or ten months, Oliver was the victim of a systematic course of treachery and deception.

In this example chosen from chapter 2, out of the same feeling or emotion, the author also used the negative words "course of treachery and deception" to describe the world and society Oliver will come down to. Oliver has been a victim of the social system and environment since he was born. The expressions accord with the weak group were always bullied and deceived. At the same time, the deteriorating social phenomena was criticized.

Example-2

'Oliver ... a new burden having been imposed upon the parish...'; '...a parish child – the orphan of a workhouse – the humble half-starved drudge – to be cuffed and buffeted through the world, - despised by all, and pitied by none.

In this example, the author told us Oliver was born and survived. And subsequently he became a new burden of the parish. The negative expressions 'new burden', 'orphan of a workhouse', 'humble half-starved drudge' and 'cuffed and buffet' etc all reflect the little boy Oliver's plight. It seems that the guilty was should be imposing to Oliver although he did nothing.

Which implies the unfair treatment Oliver suffered.[2]

Example-3

You have raised an artificial soul and spirit in him, ma'am, unbecoming a person of his condition...," "No!" replied Oliver, boldly".

In this case, the expression 'an artificial soul and spirit reflects the author's high praise for Oliver. In the face of result, the rebellious spirit was awakened in the child's heart, he is not weak

anymore. In the same way, the bold response 'no' presented a brave image to us. The author expressed his positive feelings to Oliver, who is becoming stronger after experiencing such tribulation.

Example-4

'Oh! God forgive this wretched man!' cried the boy with a burst of tears.

In this case, when Oliver went to visit the prisoner old Jwent he cried with a burst of tears, the two words 'wretched', and 'forgive' in the sentence 'God forgive this wretched man' present a kind image to us. Although experienced a very tragic life and was cheated by the old Jew, Oliver didn't lose his nature and still keep his kindness to the old man and the world.

Therefore, in this part, the author expressed his positive feelings explicitly or implicitly to Oliver by using these attitudinal words.

Example-5

That Oliver Twist was moved to resignation by the example of these good people, I can not, although I am his biographer, undertake to affirm with any degree of confidence; but I can most distinctly say, that for many months he continued meekly to submit to the domination and ill-treatment of Noah Claypole...' [3]

The meaning of the sentence is that although Oliver has been dominated and treated unfairly for several months, the author is not sure whether he will struggle against violent repression of those 'good' people or not. The implied meaning is that as a member of the Vulnerable groups in the society with such background, maybe he dared not voice his dissatisfaction or didn't have the strength to resist.

Here the word 'good' is used ironically to express the cruelty and atrocity. Actually, the author showed a kind of sympathetic feeling to the poor boy as well as the criticism to the dark society.

The research materials in this part are mainly chosen from chapters 6 and 7 (the author described the process Oliver was irritated and resulted by Noah as well as his rebellion to unfair treatment).

Actually as the weakest group and most difficult group in the society, Oliver has been bearing the injustice from the beginning, he just couldn't tolerate people insulting his mother, so his rebellious spirit comes from his nature, just as the author described 'his spirit was roused at last; the cruel insult to his dead mother had set his blood on fire'. Therefore, in this part, the author chose many negative words to describe Noah with the purpose of implying Oliver's tenacity or refractory as well as his support and sympathy to the little boy.

In a nutshell, we can say that the latest thought of the novel is Dickens' humanity spirit to the poor and his critique spirit to the society was revealed under the analysis of the appraise system. According to this study, the author interacts with the readers indirectly, which realizes the new development of the discourse comprehension in terms of interpersonal meaning.

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